

IUC 05: Towards better digital infrastructures and workflows for experimental labs

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The journey towards digitalization and efficient research data management (RDM) in experimental materials science is a multifaceted challenge. Researchers rely on diverse instruments, scientific workflows, data processing methods, and storage systems. Such a fragmented infrastructure makes it difficult to develop a standardized practical approach to digital transformation across all MSE labs. In addition, technicians, doctoral students, staff scientists, and professors may face different problems in their digitalization endeavors and cannot sufficiently benefit from the one-size-fits-all solution. Therefore, a training program tailored to the specific needs of scientists is required to bridge the gap between traditional experimental practices and modern RDM solutions.

The MatWerk Travelling Academy initiative developed a two-session training format to address this challenge:

1. The first training session engages researchers to comprehensively identify and assess their daily pain points. Through several rounds of self-evaluation moderated by experienced trainers, participants pinpoint specific hurdles impeding their digitalization progress.

2. The second session is designed to respond directly to the identified pain points. The trainers provide targeted teaching modules and customized solutions, ranging from conventional lectures, instructions, and software suggestions to direct support with the implementation.

By addressing the unique pain points of experimental materials scientists, this initiative aims to effectively improve their research data literacy and empower them to employ digital tools to streamline research workflows. Consequently, the initiative enhances data

management practices in research laboratories and supports the transition of the MSE community towards FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles. Furthermore, the training format allows for collecting information on the specific challenges that occur while establishing a digital infrastructure, thus strengthening the user-centric focus during solution development.

The initiative is progressing according to a well-defined timeline:

1. The training concept and a rollout plan were established through strategic meetings of the Travelling Academy team in the fall of 2023.
2. TU Darmstadt was selected as an initial test institution. The team members developed the workshop's training plan throughout the winter of 2024. Four experienced trainers have been assembled from the Academy team members to lead the first training session and provide their expertise and support.
3. In February 2024, the first training session took place, where participants shared the topics of their research projects and explained the adopted RDM practices. Through collaborative exercises, participants worked out instrument-to-publication pipelines and data maps and finally identified key pain points to be addressed with the help of the trainers.
4. After the first session, the Academy thoroughly reviewed the identified pain points. Teaching materials and solutions were developed to address these issues and requirements, setting the stage for the upcoming teaching workshop.

After the initial rollout, the team plans subsequent visits to other institutions to expand its reach to a larger number of experimental materials science laboratories. The collected insights from the pilot workshops will allow to adapt the future curriculum and ensure that the training program remains responsive to the evolving needs of experimental materials scientists.

In addition, the Travelling Academy plans a hackathon by the end of 2024 to complement the previous efforts and engage with the broader community. The hackathon will bring together teams of participants with varying backgrounds to address several predefined RDM challenges during intense, time-limited collaborations. Through hands-on training and collaborative problem-solving, participants will learn to apply digital tools and RDM knowledge to develop creative solutions for those challenges. By the end of a hackathon, teams will present their solutions to validate their developments and identify promising ideas that can be further refined. The participants will also gain an opportunity to network and establish connections with other experts that extend beyond the duration of the hackathon itself.

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